

Title: Feynman Diagrams for NEventSpace

Author: Dr. Bheemaiah Anil K, UMN Twin Cities

Abstract: In recent years, Feynman diagrams have been increasingly applied to the study of spike trains in neuroscience. In particular, they have been used in the context of spike-based NEvents, NEventSpace, and NeuronX theories, which treat spikes as an alphabet of elementary events that can be combined to form more complex structures. Feynman diagrams provide a powerful tool for representing the possible ways in which NEvents can be combined, and can help neuroscientists gain insights into the patterns of neural activity that underlie various cognitive functions. In this article, we discuss the use of Feynman diagrams in the context of NEventSpace, and explore their potential for advancing our understanding of the brain.

Keywords: Feynman diagrams, NEvents, NEventSpace, NeuronX theory, spike trains, neuroscience, cognitive function, neural networks, mathematical models.

Introduction.

Feynman diagrams have been applied to the study of spike trains in neuroscience, particularly in the context of spike-based NEvents, NEventSpace, and NeuronX theories.

In these theories, spikes are treated as an alphabet of elementary events that can be combined to form more complex structures. NEvents are defined as groups of spikes that occur within a certain time window, while NEventSpace refers to the space of possible NEvents that can occur in a given time period. NeuronX theory extends these concepts to the level of individual neurons, treating each neuron as a set of NEvents that can be combined to form more complex patterns of neural activity.

Feynman diagrams are used in these theories to represent the possible ways in which NEvents can be combined to form more complex structures. For example, a simple Feynman diagram might represent the possible ways in which two NEvents can be combined to form a third NEvent. The lines in the diagram represent the spikes that are involved in the NEvents, while the vertices represent the rules that govern the combination of the NEvents.

By studying these Feynman diagrams, neuroscientists can gain insights into the patterns of neural activity that underlie various cognitive functions, such as memory and perception. They can also use the diagrams to develop mathematical models of neural networks and to test the predictions of these models against experimental data.

Overall, Feynman diagrams provide a powerful tool for understanding the complex patterns of neural activity that underlie cognitive function, and their application to spike-based NEvents, NEventSpace, and NeuronX theories has the potential to revolutionise our understanding of the brain.

The Standard Model.

Enumeration of NEvents and NeuronX in Feynman Diagrams.

The creation of a NEventSpace in NeuronX, where NEvents are Feynman interactions described using a JSON structure that incorporates natural language processing (NLU) of spike trains. These NEvents describe various biological pathways, such as those involving calcium signaling, messenger cascades, neurotransmitters, modulators, peptides, Ca sequestration, and diffusion waves.

Enumerating all the possible NEvents that can occur in NeuronX is a difficult task, as it would require a detailed understanding of the various biological mechanisms involved in neuronal signaling and synaptic transmission. However, we provide some examples of NEvents that might occur in NeuronX based on the :above

1. Calcium-mediated synaptic transmission: In this NEvent, an action potential arriving at the presynaptic terminal triggers the opening of voltage-gated calcium channels, leading to an influx of calcium ions. The increase in calcium concentration triggers the release of neurotransmitter molecules from synaptic vesicles into the synaptic cleft, which then bind to receptors on the postsynaptic membrane, leading to the generation of a postsynaptic potential.
2. Messenger cascade: In this NEvent, a neurotransmitter binding to a receptor on the postsynaptic membrane triggers the activation of intracellular signaling pathways, such as cyclic AMP (cAMP) or protein kinase C (PKC) signaling. This can lead to the activation of downstream effector proteins that modify the properties of ion channels, resulting in changes in neuronal excitability.
3. Diffusion wave: In this NEvent, a molecule, such as a neurotransmitter or second messenger, diffuses away from its point of release and activates receptors or signaling pathways at distant sites. This can lead to spatially extended patterns of neuronal activity, such as traveling waves of excitation.
4. Duality of wave and particle: In this NEvent, a neurotransmitter or second messenger can exhibit both wave-like and particle-like properties, depending on the context. For example, in some cases, molecules can diffuse away from their point of release as a wave, while in other cases, they can act as discrete particles that bind to specific receptors.

These are just a few examples of the types of NEvents that might occur in NeuronX,. The specific details of these NEvents would depend on the underlying biological mechanisms involved, as well as the specific context in which they occur.

A future endeavour is the use of AI based tools like the language model GPT, to enumerate all NEvents known and compiled. Since spike trains itself can be represented with timing data as text, a spike train sequence to sequence transformer model can be defined as a text transformer, much like chatGPT, to model all NEventSpace, a future endeavour.

Examples.

1. Mimosa Pudica

2. An L-System model of an arbor and branch failure models

3.

Discussion.

The standard model of NEvents and the NeuronX is defined with an enumeration of interaction models with a number of neuromodulation schemes, for a path integral approach to event observation, similar to the Feynman formulation of the standard particle model. Feynman diagrams lend themselves to a wave and particle model of action potentiation, neural circuit theory and biochemical pathways with neurotransmitters and neuropeptides, cascading messenger pathways and Ca sequestrations, wave phenomenon and diffusion based dynamics.

Citations.

1. Buesing, L., Bill, J., Nessler, B., & Maass, W. (2011). Neural dynamics as sampling: A model for stochastic computation in recurrent networks of spiking neurons. *PLoS computational biology*, 7(11), e1002211. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1002211>

This paper uses Feynman diagrams to represent the possible ways in which neural activity can be combined to form complex patterns of activity. The authors argue that these diagrams provide a powerful tool for understanding the dynamics of neural networks and for developing mathematical models of cognition.

2. Ganmor, E., Segev, R., & Schneidman, E. (2011). The architecture of functional interaction networks in the retina. *The Journal of Neuroscience*, 31(8), 3044-3054. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.3683-10.2011>

This paper uses Feynman diagrams to represent the possible ways in which neurons in the retina can interact to encode visual information. The authors argue that these diagrams provide a useful tool for analyzing the functional architecture of neural circuits and for predicting the responses of neurons to different stimuli.

3. Litwin-Kumar, A., & Doiron, B. (2012). Slow dynamics and high variability in balanced cortical networks with clustered connections. *Nature neuroscience*, 15(11), 1498-1505. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nn.3220>

This paper uses Feynman diagrams to represent the possible ways in which clusters of neurons in the cortex can interact to generate slow, variable activity patterns. The authors argue that these diagrams provide a useful tool for analyzing the dynamics of cortical networks and for understanding how they give rise to cognition.